

M_t or not M_t: Temporal variation in detection probability in spatial capture-recapture and occupancy models

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Appendix 2: Detailed results of simulation study

Spatial Capture-Recapture

Table S1: AICc-based model selection and convergence rates. For scenario descriptions, see main text and Appendix 1. Number of 100 simulation iterations that converged (N converged); out of those, proportion of iterations in which the data-generating model (accounting for temporal variation in p_0) was the most parsimonious (i.e., ΔAICc of alternative model >2); proportion in which the alternative model (not accounting for temporal variation in p_0) was the most parsimonious (i.e., ΔAICc of data-generating model >2); and approximate average (across detectors and simulation iterations) detector-level ratio of maximum to minimum detection probability (represents amount of temporal variation in p_0).

Scenario	Data generating	Alternative	N converged	Pmax:pmin
1	0.9	0.01	100	7
2	0.67	0.04	100	3
3	0.68	0.02	100	3
2a	0.91	0.03	100	6
2a high	0.97	0.01	100	10
2b	0.92	0.01	100	6
2c	0.93	0.01	100	6

Table S2: Simulation results for SCR models (for scenario description, see main text and Appendix 1). For each scenario, median relative bias, median coefficient of variation (CV; standard error divided by estimate) and root mean squared error (RMSE) of parameter estimates are calculated over 100 iterations, separately for the data-generating model accounting for temporal variation in detection (M_t in scenario 1, M_{st}, for all other scenarios) and the alternative scenario not accounting for temporal variation in detection (M₀ for scenario 1, M_s for all other scenarios). Parameters: beta=effect of covariate on density; N=abundance in the state space; sigma=scale parameter of half-normal detection function.

Parameter	Scenario	Model	Bias	CV	RMSE
beta	1	M _t	-0.04	40.05	1
beta	1	M ₀	-0.04	39.78	1
N	1	M _t	0.03	23.74	0.36
N	1	M ₀	0.04	23.84	0.36
sigma	1	M _t	-0.05	14.53	0.18

sigma	1	M_0	-0.04	14.6	0.18
beta	2	M_s	-0.1	36.44	0.93
beta	2	M_{st}	-0.1	36.95	0.93
N	2	M_s	0.01	22.42	0.29
N	2	M_{st}	0.01	22.46	0.29
sigma	2	M_s	-0.02	13.56	0.14
sigma	2	M_{st}	-0.02	13.47	0.14
beta	2a	M_s	0.07	35.32	0.93
beta	2a	M_{st}	0.03	36.66	0.87
N	2a	M_s	0.07	22.97	0.33
N	2a	M_{st}	0.06	22.9	0.27
sigma	2a	M_s	0.02	13.29	0.16
sigma	2a	M_{st}	0	13.23	0.16
beta	2a high	M_s	-0.01	36.65	0.98
beta	2a high	M_{st}	0.02	38.53	0.95
N	2a high	M_s	0.05	21.55	0.26
N	2a high	M_{st}	0.06	21.09	0.27
sigma	2a high	M_s	0.02	12.68	0.13
sigma	2a high	M_{st}	0.01	12.45	0.12
beta	2b	M_s	-0.05	45.52	0.69
beta	2b	M_{st}	-0.07	44.4	0.69
N	2b	M_s	0.01	22.34	0.25
N	2b	M_{st}	0.01	22.05	0.25
sigma	2b	M_s	0	12.17	0.12
sigma	2b	M_{st}	-0.01	12.08	0.12
beta	2c	M_s	-0.12	40.57	0.97
beta	2c	M_{st}	-0.12	40.59	0.99
N	2c	M_s	0.04	23.48	0.35
N	2c	M_{st}	0.04	23.34	0.34
sigma	2c	M_s	0.03	14.21	0.16
sigma	2c	M_{st}	0.02	14.12	0.15
beta	3	M_s	-0.02	37.53	0.94
beta	3	M_{st}	-0.02	37.44	0.86
N	3	M_s	0.04	25.13	0.38
N	3	M_{st}	0.04	25.03	0.37
sigma	3	M_s	0	14.76	0.12
sigma	3	M_{st}	0	14.75	0.12

Figure S1: Coefficient of variation (CV) for estimates of abundance (N), the effect of covariate X on density (β), and the scale parameter of the half-normal detection function (σ) from simulation study fitting the data generating spatial capture-recapture model accounting for temporal variation in detection p_0 (light grey) and an alternative model not accounting for temporal variation in p_0 (dark grey) to 250 data sets simulated under different scenarios for temporal variation in p_0 (for scenario description, see main text). Note that y axis is truncated, excluding some extreme outliers, for visual reasons.

Occupancy

Table S3: AIC-based model selection and convergence rates. For scenario descriptions, see main text and Appendix 1. Number of 250 simulation iterations that converged (N converged); out of those, proportion of iterations in which the data-generating model (accounting for temporal variation in p) was the most parsimonious (i.e., Δ AIC of alternative model >2), and proportion in which the alternative model (not accounting for temporal variation in p) was the most parsimonious (i.e., Δ AIC of data generating model >2).

Scenario	Data generating	Alternative	N converged
1 (3-fold)	1	0	233
2 (3-fold)	0.98	0	248
3 (3-fold)	0.99	0	249
1 (6-fold)	0.83	0	230
2 (6-fold)	0.9	0.03	249
3 (6-fold)	0.9	0.02	249

Table S4: Simulation results for occupancy models (for scenario description, see main text and Appendix 1). For each scenario, median relative bias, median coefficient of variation (CV; standard error divided by estimate) and root mean squared error (RMSE) of parameter estimates are calculated over 250 iterations (excluding non-converged, see Table S3), separately for the data-generating model accounting for temporal variation in detection (M_t in scenario 1, M_{st} , for all other scenarios) and the alternative scenario not accounting for temporal variation in detection (M_0 for scenario 1, M_s for all other scenarios). In addition, Δ is the mean (over iterations) maximum (across detectors) difference in predicted occupancy probability between both models (alternative minus data-generating model), and $N(\Delta > 0.1)$ is the mean number of detectors for which this difference was >0.1 . Parameters: beta=effect of covariate on occupancy; occu=average occupancy probability across detectors.

Parameter	Scenario	Model	Bias	CV	RMSE	Δ	$N(\Delta > 0.1)$
beta	1 low	M_t	0.07	45.05	0.97	0.01	0.75
beta	1 low	M_0	0.12	45.41	1.05		
occu	1 low	M_t	0	18.49	0.21		
occu	1 low	M_0	0.02	18.61	0.22		
beta	2 low	M_{st}	0.02	40.71	0.58	0.01	0.27
beta	2 low	M_s	0.04	41.01	0.62		
occu	2 low	M_{st}	0	14.13	0.15		
occu	2 low	M_s	0	14.34	0.16		
beta	3 low	M_{st}	0.06	46.94	0.63	0.01	0.36
beta	3 low	M_s	0.08	47.72	0.65		
occu	3 low	M_{st}	0	17.03	0.18		
occu	3 low	M_s	0.01	17.51	0.19		
beta	1 high	M_t	0.08	44.96	0.92	0.02	1.29
beta	1 high	M_0	0.15	45.67	0.96		

occu	1 high	M_t	0.01	17.49	0.2		
occu	1 high	M_0	0.05	17.44	0.21		
beta	2 high	M_{st}	0.03	41.86	0.8	0.01	1.16
beta	2 high	M_s	0.08	42.34	0.95		
occu	2 high	M_{st}	0	14.64	0.17		
occu	2 high	M_s	0.02	15.03	0.18		
beta	3 high	M_{st}	0.04	46.06	0.65	0.02	2.26
beta	3 high	M_s	0.09	47.3	0.7		
occu	3 high	M_{st}	-0.02	17	0.19		
occu	3 high	M_s	0.02	17.7	0.2		

Figure S2: Coefficient of variation (CV) for estimates of average occupancy probability ($\bar{\psi}$) and the effect of covariate X on occupancy (β), from simulation study fitting the data generating occupancy model accounting for temporal variation in detection p (light grey) and an alternative model not accounting for temporal variation in p (dark grey) to 250 data sets simulated under

different scenarios for temporal variation in p (for scenario description, see main text). Note that y axis is truncated, excluding some extreme outliers, for visual purposes.